

One-Pot Synthesis of Symmetrical Azines Using MPy-Ts Catalyst: Facile and Highly Efficient methodology

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Abstract:

Azines are valuable compounds in synthetic chemistry and industry, and the development of greener synthetic methods remains important. In this work, a novel solid acid catalyst, MPy-Ts, was designed and synthesized for the first time and applied to the one-pot synthesis of symmetrical azines via direct condensation of aldehydes with hydrazine hydrate. The reaction proceeds through *in situ* Schiff base formation followed by azine formation with elimination of water. The MPy-Ts catalyst showed excellent efficiency, providing high yields in short reaction times under simple conventional conditions. The method is cost-effective, robust process and ease of operation for isolation of pure product. The structures of MPy-Ts and the synthesized azines were confirmed by FTIR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and ESI-MS analyses.

Keywords: Azines, good yield, homogeneous catalysis, symmetrical azines, one-pot,

1. Introduction

In organic synthesis, azines, R₁-C=N-N=C-R₂, have garnered a lot of interest because they are effective synthons for manufacturing heterocyclic compounds like pyrazoles, purines, and pyrimidines. These substances make up a significant class of substances with surprising biological properties. [1-3]. The Azine is important candidate showing numerous biological activities. The some Azine containing compounds **A**, **B**, **C** showed anticancer activity, Compound **D** and **E** exhibited Anti-glycating Activity, compounds **G**, **H** and **F** revealed Anti-diabetic properties, compound **I** reported as Cholinesterase Inhibitory Activities, compound **J**

and **K** reported Urease Inhibitory and Cholinesterase Inhibitory activities. [4-14], **Figure 1** showed the biologically active azine containing compounds.

Azines have recently sparked a lot of interest in the development of covalent organic frameworks (COFs) that can function as chemo sensing detectors or have photocatalytic activity. [15-16] The usual method for the preparation of azines involves treatment of carbonyl compounds with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of catalyst.[17]. A number of methods have been reported for the synthesis of azines under various conditions, but most of them require elevated temperatures and complex catalysts. Hence, there is a need to develop a simple, eco-friendly method under mild conditions for the preparation of azines. Apart from that, very few other pathways were documented, such as the conversion of a tetrazole with cyclooctyne or the interaction of diazoalkanes with carbenoids or carbenes. All of these techniques, however, are restricted to a small number of extremely particular substrates and lack universality. [18-23] Now the research in organic synthesis is mainly focused on the use of environmental benign catalysts under solvent free conditions. [24-27] The development of ecologically safe processes to convert widely available starting materials into synthetically useful products is one of the main obstacles in the field of catalysis.

Figure 1: Azine containing biologically active compounds

2.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in reaction **scheme 1**. N-Methyl pyrrolidinone was dissolved in toluene at room temperature. To this solution, p-toluenesulfonic acid was added with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was then heated to 60 to 65°C and maintained at this temperature for 2 hours. After completion of the reaction, toluene was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting brown oily mass was allowed to cool to room temperature, after which methyl tert-butyl ether (50 mL) was added. Formation of a solid was observed. The slurry was stirred for 30 minutes, then filtered, and the solid was washed with methyl tert-butyl ether (10 mL). An off-white solid was obtained after drying crystalline solid and was characterized by ¹H NMR. The NH proton appeared at $\delta = 7.5$ (S, 1H) in ¹HNMR, confirming that P-Toluenesulfonic acid condensed with N-Methyl pyrrolidinone. The molecular weight of catalyst was confirmed by mass spectroscopy (M+1) 271.33, and IR showed NH stretching frequency at 3662.16 cm⁻¹. The catalyst was isolated by filtration of reaction mass in toluene. A Freshly prepared catalyst for the reaction is preferred for quantitative conversion, which reduces reaction time.

Scheme1. Synthesis of 1-Methyl-2-Oxopyrrolidin-1-ium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate [Mpy-Ts] catalyst.

Herein, we present the first direct synthesis of azines derivatives (**BD-1 to BD-10**) from substituted aromatic aldehydes. The reaction is based on imine formation followed by azine from aldehyde and hydrazine catalyzed by A, 1-Methyl-2-oxopyrrolidin-1-ium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate (MPy-Ts). This one-step process produces water as by-product and forms azines directly from easily accessible, sustainable starting materials, making it both atom-efficient and environmentally benign. Mechanistic insight is given, including the surprising role of catalyst and the participation of hydrogen bonding in this process, which has resulted in the isolation of a crystalline substance. The synthetic route for azine derivatives using **MPy-Ts** as catalyst is represented in **Scheme 2**.

Scheme 2: Synthetic route for azine derivatives (**BD-1 to BD-10**) using **MPy-Ts** as catalyst

Figure 2: Structural representation of synthesized azine derivatives (**BD-1 to BD-10**)

To investigate this synthetic methodology, it was required to employ a suitable solvent, and reaction conditions are summarized in this article. We conducted the reaction without a catalyst using 4-F-benzaldehyde (**4**) and hydrazine hydrate (**3**) as per the general procedure for the synthesis of 1,2-Bis(2-Fluorobenzylidene)Hydrazine (**BD-1**). The synthesis scheme represented in **scheme 3**.

Scheme 3: Synthesis of 1,2-bis(2,4,6-trichlorobenzylidene)hydrazine (**BD-1**)

In **Table 1**, effect of different catalysts on the synthesis of **BD-1** from hydrazine carbothioamide was examined under similar reaction conditions, and the results are summarized in **Table 1**. In the absence of a catalyst, the rate of reaction was very slowly and afforded **BD-1** as **50%** of yield after 10 h. After using acetic acid, sulphuric acid, and hydrochloric acid improved the yield but required either prolonged reaction times or higher temperatures. Anthranilic acid also gave a good yield, although the reaction needed **24 h** for completion. In contrast, **MPy-Ts** showed superior catalytic efficiency, delivering **BD-1** in **95%** yield within just 1.5 h under relatively mild conditions. These results clearly demonstrate that **MPy-Ts** is a more effective catalyst for this transformation compared to the other systems examined.

Table 1. Synthesis of Compound **BD-1** using Hydrazine carbothioamide and MPy-Ts

Entry	Catalyst	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)	Solvent	Yield (%)
1	Without catalyst	77-80	10	Ethanol	50
2	Acetic acid	80-82	24	Ethanol	95
3	Sulphuric acid	78-80	10	Ethanol	91
4	Hydrochloric acid	85-87	7.5	Ethanol	76
5	Anthranilic acid	65	24	Ethanol	90
6	MPy-Ts	70-80	1.5	Ethanol	95

From the solvent screening results shown in **Table 2**, it is clear that the choice of solvent has a strong effect on the reaction outcome. Ethanol performed best among all the solvents tested, giving **BD-1** in **95%** yield within just 1 h. In comparison, acetic acid, toluene, and acetonitrile required longer reaction times and resulted in slightly lower yields. The use of polar aprotic solvents such as **DMF** and **DMSO** was less favorable, as the reaction proceeded more slowly and the yields were reduced. Overall, ethanol was identified as the most suitable solvent for the **MPy-Ts** catalyzed synthesis of **BD-1**, offering both faster completion and higher yield.

Table 2. Screening of solvents for synthesis of **BD-1** in the presence of MPy-Ts

Entry	Solvent	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
1	Acetonitrile	4.0	85
2	Toluene	2.5	83
3	Acetic acid	2.0	86
4	DMF	3.5	84
5	DMSO	4.0	80
6	Ethanol	1.0	95

3. Experimental section

3.1 General information

The starting materials substituted aldehydes, hydrazine hydrate and other raw materials were procured from sigma Aldrich. Solvents was GC grade and used without additional purification. The FTIR spectrum was recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400S spectrometer using the KBr disc technique. The nuclear magnetic resonance spectra (^1H and ^{13}C NMR) were obtained on a Bruker instrument (at 400 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively) with CDCl_3 as solvent and tetramethyl silane as standard. Original analytical data are available for inspection in the Supplementary Materials.

General Procedure for the Synthesis of N-methyl-pyrrolidinone Tosylate

N-methyl-pyrrolidinone (1.0 g, 0.0101 mol) was dissolved in 25 mL of toluene at room temperature under stirring. To this solution, P-toluenesulfonic acid (1.7 g, 0.0098 mol) was added slowly with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was heated to 60-65 °C and maintained at this temperature for 2hr. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC using DCM:MeOH (9:1) as the mobile phase.

After completion, the solvent (toluene) was distilled off under reduced pressure to afford a brown oily residue. The residue was cooled to room temperature, and 50 mL of methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE) was added, leading to the formation of a solid. The slurry was stirred for 30 min, filtered, and washed with additional MTBE (10 mL). The resulting off-white solid

was dried to afford N-methyl-morpholine tosylate. The yield was calculated and compared with the theoretical yield. The product was confirmed by spectral analyses (FTIR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, and ESI-MS) for structural confirmation, FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): $\nu = 3666.16, 2361.64, 1041$ (S=O), 1875.23, ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ : 9.139 (s, 1H, NH), 7.524 -7.141 (Ar-4H) 3.2-3.1 (t, 2H), 2.6 (s, 3H), 2.29 (s, 3H), 2.2 (t, 2H), 1.9-1.8 (m, 2H). ^{13}C -NMR (125 MHz, DMSO,) δ : 144.71, 138.37, 128.33, 48.60, 40.12- 38.87, 30.02, 29.00, 23.34, 20.52. ESI-MS (M+1) = 271.33.

General procedure for synthesis azine derivatives (BD-1 to BD-10)

20 mmol of hydrazine monohydrate was added substituted aryl aldehydes 10 mmol in 30 mL of ethanol, then catalytic amount of MPy-Ts was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir for 3-4 hours until substituted aryl aldehydes has been consumed. Thin layer chromatography (TLC). After the completion of the reaction, the precipitates were filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to afford target compounds, respectively. In a case where the solids did not form during the reaction, ethanol was evaporated under vacuum and the formed solids recrystallized from ethanol

Spectral data

N-methyl-pyrrolidinone Tosylate (MPy-Ts)

FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): $\nu = 3666.16, 2361.64, 1041$ (S=O), 1875.23, ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ : 9.139 (s, 1H, NH), 7.524 -7.141 (Ar-4H) 3.2-3.1 (t, 2H), 2.6 (s, 3H), 2.29 (s, 3H), 2.2 (t, 2H), 1.9-1.8 (m, 2H). ^{13}C -NMR (125 MHz, DMSO,) δ : 144.71, 138.37, 128.33, 48.60, 40.12- 38.87, 30.02, 29.00, 23.34, 20.52. ESI-MS (M+1) = 271.33.

1,2-Bis(2-Fluorobenzylidene)Hydrazine (BD-1)

Yellow solid; yield: 63%; IR cm^{-1} : 1625.88 cm^{-1} (C=N); ^1H -NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.89 (s, 2H, CH=N), 8.09 (t, $J = 7.26$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.42 (td, $J_{\text{H-F}} = 1.31, 6.87$, Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.20 (t, 7.56 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.10-7.09 (t, 8.94, 2H, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 162.36 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 254.7$ Hz), 155.69 (C=N), 132.97 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 8.68$ Hz), 127.81 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.24$ Hz), 124.48 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.54$ Hz), 121.86 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 9.80$ Hz), 116.02 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.15$ Hz); HRMS Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{F}_2$ [M +H], found: 245.0.

1,2-bis(2-chlorobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-2)

Yellow solid; yield: 90%; IR cm^{-1} : 1617.86 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.09 (s, 2H, CH=N-7), 8.22 (d, $J=7.71$ Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.43 (d, $J=7.99$ Hz, 2H, ArH) 7.39 (dt, $J=1.63, 7.99$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H) 7.34 (t, $J=7.53$ Hz, Ar-H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.13 (C=N), 135.91, 132.28, 131.35, 130.09, 128.38, 127.08; HRMS Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]$, found: 277.0.

1,2-Bis(3-Methylbenzylidene)Hydrazine (BD-3)

Yellow solid; yield: 83%, IR cm^{-1} : 1623.06 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.63 (s, 2H, CH=N), 7.68 (s, 2H, Ar- H), 7.61(d, $J=7.56$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H) 7.34 (t, $J=7.56$ Hz, 2H), 7.27 (d, $J=7.50$ Hz, 2H), 2.40 (s, 6H, CH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 162.26 (C=N), 138.55, 134.23, 134.05, 132.09, 128.81, 128.70, 126.09, 21.33; HRMS Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]$, found: 237.1.

1,2-bis(2-nitrobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-4)

Yellow solid; yield: 75%; IR cm^{-1} : 1629.43 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.12 (s, 2H, CH=N), 8.30 (d, $J=7.8$ Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 8.11 (d, $J=8.22$ Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.76 (t, $J=7.50$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.66–7.63 (m, 2H, Ar- H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 158.40 (C=N), 149.12, 133.56, 131.55, 129.60, 128.69, 124.79; HRMS (ESI-qTOF): Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]$ found: 488.3072.

1,2-bis(3-nitrobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-5)

Yellow solid; yield: 78%, IR cm^{-1} : 1624.82 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.73 (s, 2H, CH=N, 2H-Ar), 8.35 (dd, $J=1.08, 8.16$ Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 8.19 (d, $J=7.68$ Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.69 (t, $J=7.92$, 2H, Ar- H), $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 160.56 (C=N), 148.71, 135.51, 134.20, 129.95, 125.80, 123.24; HRMS (ESI-qTOF): Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]$ found: 321.0660.

1,2-bis(4-fluorobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-6)

Yellow solid; yield: 93%; IR cm^{-1} : 1693.36 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.60 (s, 2H, CH=N), 7.83 (dd, $J_{\text{H-F}}=5.6, 8.49$ Hz, 4H, Ar- H), 7.13 (t, $J_{\text{H-F}}=8.64$ Hz, 4H, Ar- H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (157 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 164.71 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}=252.14$ Hz), 160.95 (C=N), 130.67

(d, J_{C-F} =8.83 Hz), 130.15 (d, J_{C-F} =2.60 Hz), 116.08 (d, J_{C-F} =22.12 Hz); HRMS (ESI-qTOF): Calcd for $C_{14}H_{11}N_2F_2$ [M +H] , found: 245.09.

1,2-bis(4-chlorobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-7)

Yellow solid; yield: 95%; IR cm^{-1} : 1623.43 cm^{-1} (C=N); 1H -NMR (600 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.54 (s, 2H, CH=N), 7.72 (d, J =8.04 Hz, 4H, Ar- H), 7.41 (d, J =8.04 Hz, 4H, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (157 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 161.05 (C=N), 137.35, 132.48, 129.75, 129.15; HRMS Calcd for $C_{14}H_{11}N_2 Cl_2$ [M +H]⁺, found: 277.11.

1,2-bis(2,4-dichlorobenzylidene)hydrazine (BD-8)

Yellow solid; yield: 92%; IR cm^{-1} : 1614.94 cm^{-1} (C=N); 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 9.02 (s, 2H, CH=N), 8.18 (d, J =8.41 Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.46 (s, 2H, Ar- H), 7.34 (d, J =7.48 Hz, 2H, Ar- H); ^{13}C NMR (157 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 158.36 (C=N), 137.88, 136.42, 129.93, 129.89, 129.18, 127.67; HRMS Calcd for $C_{14}H_9N_2Cl_4$ [M +H]⁺ found: 346.56

1,2-Bis(3-Bromobenzylidene)Hydrazine (BD-9)

Yellow solid; yield: 56%; IR cm^{-1} : 1625.24 cm^{-1} (C=N); 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.55 (s, 2H, CH=N), 8.01 (s, 2H, Ar-H), (d, J =7.70 Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.58 (dd, J =0.78, 7.98 Hz, 2H, A- H), 7.32 (t, J =7.80 Hz, 2H, A- H); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 160.94 (C=N), 135.98, 134.20, 131.09, 130.31, 127.44, 123.04; HRMS Calcd for $C_{14}H_{11}N_2Br_2$ [M +H]⁺, found: 367.36.

1,2-Bis(2-Bromobenzylidene)Hydrazine (BD-10)

Yellow solid; yield: 87%, IR cm^{-1} : 1610.51 cm^{-1} (C=N); 1H -NMR (600 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 9.02 (s, 2H, CH=N), 8.20 (d, J =7.74 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.62 (d, J =7.88 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.39 (t, J =7.44 Hz, 2H, Ar- H), 7.31 (t, J =7.25 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), ^{13}C NMR (157 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 161.37 (C=N), 133.33, 132.91, 132.42, 128.75, 127.66, 125.83; HRMS Calcd for $C_{14}H_{11}N_2Br_2$ [M +H]⁺found: 365.276

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